

Case Study

Impact of Social Media on Business Performance: A Case Study on Arki Group

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Abstract

Social media are becoming a critical avenue for business enterprises to promote their products and services. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of social media on business performance in Arki Group. Questionnaires were distributed to a specific group of managers, marketing personnel, affiliated manufacturers, and subcontractors that collaborate with Arki Group for collecting quantitative data. Five-point Likert scale have been used. Purposive sampling was used to choose the respondents and the study period was 2023. Study found that social media does not increase significantly brand image, connectivity between business and customers, facilitate marketing, the chance of fraud business, and following of trends. It also does not assist substantially the entrepreneurs. These insignificant impacts are obvious as Bangladesh is a country characterized by low digital literacy rate. However social media influences the price of products. The study has managerial and social implications as managers of firms can effectively utilize social media to determine competitive price. Customers' connectivity through social media creates indirect pressure on producers to provide society's desired product at competitive prices. This study shed new light on the effect of social media on performance of an asset management company.

Keywords: Connectivity, Firm, Fraud, Performance, Social Media Marketing.

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Introduction

In present era of digitization and globalization, the internet has a significant impact on how people interact and form connections. In their daily lives, individuals of various nationalities, ethnicities, and ages have embraced it enthusiastically, finding it useful for fostering and sustaining relationships both personally and professionally. The accessibility of these new technical developments has created connectivity and appealing to everybody, including commercial practices inside enterprises. Public relations via social media have replaced traditional business communication techniques in the sector. Since the advent of social networking, it has become the new frontier in business. The number of individuals communicating with one another on social media initially contributed to its success. Businesses soon realized the degree of online attention that social media sites were getting and the potential attention that social media may have (Narayanan, et al., 2012). Online traffic thus became valuable in terms of money. Since then, the use of social media marketing for online advertising has increased. Through interactive computer platforms, people may produce and exchange information, ideas, hobbies, and other kinds of expression by making use of online networks and communities. Nowadays, the majority of businesses are making equal attempts to utilize these sites because it has been shown to have clear benefits. In general, web-based social networking is altering the ways in which we communicate, collaborate, consume, and create. They highlight one of the most notable and revolutionary implications of data innovation on business, both within and outside company boundaries.

Campbell et al., (2011) stated that the technology itself is less important than what people are doing with it since users are now producing and consuming content instead of just obtaining it, which adds value to the websites that allow them to do so. Sinclair and Vogus (2011) stated “social media is a broad term that describes software tools that create user-generated content that can be shared.” A social network website needs to have certain fundamental features such as user profiles, content, a way for users to interact with one another and leave comments on each other's pages, and the ability to join online communities based on desires in things like politics or fashion. Social media marketing means using social sites to increase traffic or attention. A firm has to be well informed about social media in order to consider it as a marketing strategy. Web 2.0 is a concept that represents a new way that end users utilize the internet, where material is continually amended by all operators in a sharing and collaborative fashion. Understanding social media requires first understanding Web 2.0. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Web 2.0 has progressed beyond basic information retrieval to working together, interaction, and compatibility. (Campbell et al. 2011).

Social media is becoming an attractive platform for many business organizations as it facilitates in creating awareness about business activities, promoting products, collecting feedback from the market, and enhance connectivity among different stakeholders to a significant extent. In year 2024, the growth rate of social media user was 22.3% and the total number of users was 52.9 million which is a significant proportion of total population (The Daily Star, 25/10/2024). The social media users' review about the firms' products or services have an immense effect on existing and potential users which in-turn have an impact on firms' sales revenue. Moreover, social media enhances 'word-of-mouth marketing' and 'de-marketing'. End-users of products are relying on social media to make

their purchase decision from a set of alternative options. So, eventually the market share of a company largely depends on it. Knowing this fact, the corporations are spending heavily on social media advertising. It is anticipated that social media advertising spending in Bangladesh would reach US\$85.00 million by 2025. It is anticipated that this expenditure would expand at an annual rate of 10.04%, reaching a projected market volume of US\$124.64 million by 2029. Additionally, it is anticipated that by 2029, there would be 131.9 million users in Bangladesh's social media advertising industry. The rise in mobile internet usage in Bangladesh is greatly expanding the reach and efficacy of social media marketing initiatives (Statista, 2025).

The degree of influence by the social media depends on firm's nature of business and the type of industry to which it belongs. The choice of Fast Movable Consumer Goods (FMCG) is most likely influenced by activities in social media but the scenario might be different for real estate sector. Arki Group is a reputed builder and designer of interior decoration of a house. Bangladesh is a developing country and it suffers from digital divide. Although many firms of consumer goods industry is utilizing social media, its application to other industrial sector is not apparent. The digital implications on real estate sector in Bangladesh still is an uncovered area. The purpose of this study was to stimulate creative investigations into the relationship between online social networking and corporate performance of Arki Group. In this study, we lay forth a comprehensive research strategy to comprehend the relationships between business performance and web-based social networking. We reviewed the relevant literature that deal with the particular problem in this exploration system and identify areas that need more investigation. Although many research works have been done on effect of social media on financial and operating performance, very few researches have focused on brand image, pricing, product promotion, product authenticity, fraudulent risk and assistance to entrepreneurs. Moreover, most research works were conducted in developed countries with a high literacy rate. The aim of the present study is to fill this research gap by highlighting on the influence of social media on above-mentioned aspects in a developing country like Bangladesh and taking Arki group as a case study. The conceptual framework of the study is as follows:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework developed by researcher (modified from TAM)

Literature review

Businesses have decided that it is in their best interests to adjust to more modern marketing techniques, particularly social media marketing, since social media first gained popularity. In the 21st century, social media marketing is a crucial part of company. To acquire exposure, viability, and sustainability in the present competitive environment, small company owners are utilizing this marketing method to promote their enterprises (Taneja & Toombs, 2014). Zhu and Chen (2015) contended that in order for social media marketing to be successful, it must be consistent and matched with the various demands of social media users. Sales, connection building, brand values or reputation, and awareness are the marketing goals of social media marketing. Effective customer interaction and communication, however, is the primary goal that companies should incorporate into their social media strategies. Taneja and Toombs (2014) conducted an analysis on the significance of small companies using social media for marketing purposes. In order to successfully sell goods or services on social media, businesses need to establish a rapport with their target market. In order to effectively deploy marketing resources to relationship building, it is necessary to first correctly identify, maintain, and establish positive connections with clients (Taneja & Toombs, 2014). Businesses must shift from a product-oriented to a customer-oriented strategy if they hope to develop brand loyalty.

A highly competitive online ecosystem has been created by the widespread creation and consumption of material, where many forms of content compete with one another for the limited attention of the user community (Narayanan, et al., 2012). Companies have benefited from social media's plethora of marketing techniques. One tactic is basing their revenue model on Google-like advertisements. It didn't take long for Google, which started to dominate internet searches in the early 2000s, to identify an at the time novel method of monetizing search through online advertising (Asur, 2012). Because consumers often spend a significant amount of their precious time surfing the web, this strategy is beneficial. The number of people who regularly use the internet has grown due to the spread of social media platforms. Additionally, companies have set up social media profiles where customers may follow them and essentially use them as a platform for customer-to-business dialogue. In addition to interacting with clients, this may provide businesses a chance to observe what their rivals are doing and how they are interacting with their clientele. Flat Tummy Tea has grown at a pace of more than 400% yearly month over month since its founding in 2013. They have achieved this growth rate by adopting social media as a crucial component of their marketing strategy and by fully embracing the internet. The company's trade secret is an extremely precise procedure and ROI-based algorithm that are applied on a number of websites, particularly Instagram. Using famous people or other people with large social media followings was one of their main strategies. More than 500,000 people follow them on Instagram, many of them are brand-new clients (Gibson, 2018).

Bampo et al. (2008) looked into how an individual's transmission behavior and the digital networks' social structure—which includes random, scale-free, and tiny world—affect the effectiveness of a campaign. The results of the study verify that a viral message's ability to propagate is greatly influenced by the digital networks' social structure. In-depth qualitative interviews were used by Brown et al. (2007) to study online

word-of-mouth communication, which was then followed by a social network analysis of a single online community. Altogether, the findings offer compelling evidence that people behave as though websites are the main "actors" in virtual social networks and that virtual communities might serve as a social stand-in for personal recognition. In their study, Casaló et al. (2008) examined how customer commitment was impacted by involvement in an online community. Research indicated that engagement with a virtual society positively impacts consumers' loyalty to the brand that the community revolves around. In his research, Cha (2009) investigated if and to what extent product type influences the views people have when purchasing on social networking sites. The study found that sentiments about virtual goods are influenced by fit, simplicity of use, social networking site experience, and gender. The advantages of using social media and the internet for small enterprises operating in underserved areas were examined by Jones et al. (2015). According to the study, there are a number of advantages to using websites and social media platforms, such as increased customer awareness and inquiries, improved customer relationships, a rise in the number of new customers, improved global customer reach, and the opportunity to co-promote local businesses that improve the reputation of small businesses in the area. In his research, Stelzner (2015) polled more than 3700 marketers to see how they used social media to expand and advertise their brands. According to the survey, larger companies were far more likely to concur that their Facebook marketing campaigns were successful.

In their study, Tajvidi and Karami (2021) examined how social media affects business performance in the UK hotel sector, with marketing capabilities playing a mediating role. The findings showed a strong and favorable correlation between social media use and business performance. Nonetheless, the results demonstrated that the relationship between social media use and business success is positively and considerably mediated by marketing abilities. Zu et al. (2019) evaluated how businesses' performance was affected by varying levels of social media input. From 2010 to 2014, the researchers gathered panel data on privately traded companies from Sina Weibo. The findings demonstrated that Weibo input intensity affects company performance in a nonlinear way; more precisely, the connection between input intensity and performance is inverted U-shaped. In the context of chain stores and franchises, Wu (2016) investigated the function of social media marketing strategy and its relationships to organizational culture, strategic leadership, organizational learning, social networks, innovation orientation, and performance. The study makes use of information from 327 operational businesses in Taiwan's franchise and chain store systems. The findings indicated that one of the most important elements in boosting a company's performance in the franchise and chain store systems is its social media marketing plan.

To develop a conceptual framework of the characteristics that allow businesses to profit from utilizing social media throughout their innovation processes, Muninger et al. (2019) used a qualitative, theory-building method. Social media managers, who coordinate social media activities throughout the innovation process, are one of the tools that improve a firm's capabilities. Wang and Kim (2017) looked at how social media use may assist businesses in developing new CRM capabilities, which will enhance marketing adoption tactics and overall business success. By enhancing the beneficial effects of social CRM capabilities on business performance, they showed that social media use had a moderating effect. The usage of social media in the process of developing new products

was studied by Bashir et al. (2017). Its foundation was a thorough analysis of multinational companies (MNCs) operating in the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) industry worldwide. According to the findings, social media may be seen as an unofficial way to learn about consumer preferences, rivals' actions, industry trends, and product reviews. In their study, Choi et al. (2020) proposed a social media mining technique that uses event detection and tracking, sentiment analysis, and customer complaint management to find time-evolving product possibilities for product enhancement and competitive intelligence.

Onngam and Charoensukmongkol (2024) used a sample of 334 small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Thailand to examine how social media analytics affect business performance. The findings confirmed that social media analytics strategies had a favorable impact on business success. In their study, Susanto et al. (2023) sought to reexamine how SMEs' entrepreneurial orientation (EO) affected their performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. Findings revealed that social media use partially mediates the EO-performance nexus of SMEs and moderates the link between EO and SME performance. Yayock (2023) evaluated the impact of social media on Grat Nigerian Insurance Plc's commercial performance. A survey study approach was used with 67 employees who were chosen at random. The Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory was used in this study, and the results show that social media use can improve corporate performance, but that in order to fully realize its potential, it must be regulated.

Tehrani et al. (2024) in their research tended to examine the impact of social media usage on firm performance with the mediating role of organizational agility and innovation capability. Sample firms were chosen from German automotive industry. The findings suggest that social media usage has a substantial and positive impact on innovation capability, organizational agility, and firm performance. The impacts of social media capacity on business performance as well as the moderating influence of the CEO's social media competence were examined by Bai and Yan (2023). The results demonstrated that a company's social media presence has a favorable impact on both customer engagement and business success; the aforementioned link is considerably moderated by the social media presence of CEOs. According to Hanafizadeh et al. (2021), social media use has an impact on business performance. They put out a conceptual map that demonstrates encouraging connections between an organization's actualized level of social media maturity and the performance outcomes that follow. Performance theory and the notion of social media growth and maturity were combined to create the conceptual map.

Social media influencers (SMIs) can assist companies in cultivating positive brand perceptions, which in turn can enhance product acceptability and subsequent business success, according to an empirical study by Nafees et al. (2021). The findings, which were based on detailed survey data from 231 American Instagram users, showed that SMI power is positively correlated with customer perceptions of the brand, and that this link is largely mediated by perceived SMI competence and credibility. Prior studies on the connection between social media and business success were examined and compiled by Costanzo and Kirkland (2024). Their results show that social media use, both inside and outside of a company, can affect performance. Ahmad et al. (2018) in their study investigated the adoption of social media among SMEs in the Middle East region;

specifically, in the UAE. They also analyzed the adoption phenomena through word of mouth, viral marketing and social presence theory. The results showed how customers' opinions and purchasing intentions are influenced by electronic word-of-mouth information on social media.

To find study trends and gaps in the area of social media and company performance, Bhimani et al. (2019) conducted a comprehensive literature review. According to their results, researchers most frequently employ behavioral and resource-based theoretical lenses, and social media is viewed as both an enabler and a driver of innovation. According to empirical study by Bizzi and Labban (2019), those who use social media extensively are more likely to trade online but are also four times more likely to follow other traders mindlessly. Through the online participation of consumers, Braojos et al. (2019) offered a novel organizational theory and empirical data on how social commerce-IT skills impact business performance. Kwayu and Abubakre (2018) investigated the ways in which social media has evolved into a competitive instrument and how it affects organizational strategy and operations. The results demonstrated how social media is affecting competition through product creation and imitation.

Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

An information systems theory called the technology acceptance model (TAM) simulates how people adopt and utilize new technologies. The terminus where humans utilize the technology is the actual system use. One of the things that motivates individuals to utilize technology is behavioral intention. The attitude, or overall perception of the technology, influences the behavioral intent. According to the concept, a variety of factors, including the following, affect users' decisions about how and when to adopt new technology:

According to Fred Davis, perceived usefulness (PU) is "the extent to which an individual feels that utilizing a specific system would improve their work efficiency." It refers to a person's perception of the technology's utility for their desired task. "The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort" is Davis' definition of perceived ease-of-use (PEOU). The obstacle will be overcome if the technology is simple to use. No one will be fond of it if it is difficult to use and the interface is complex. Social influence and other external factors have a significant role in determining attitude. People will have the mindset and intention to use the technology when these factors are present. Yet, as each person is unique, the perception may vary based on age and gender.

Diffusion of Innovations Theory

E.M. Rogers, a communication theorist at the University of New Mexico, created the diffusion of innovations theory in 1962. This theory aims to clarify how and why novel concepts and methods are embraced, as well as why they may proliferate over extended periods of time. The rate at which diffusion or spreading takes place depends in large part on how innovations are conveyed to various societal segments and the subjective

perceptions around them. This theory, which describes how a new concept moves through phases of adoption by various participants or users, is commonly used by businesses when they are creating marketing strategies for new goods and expanding their market share. Innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards are the key participants in the idea.

Hypotheses of the study

Based on literature review, the hypotheses of the study are as follows:

H₁: Social media improves brand awareness

H₂: Social media increases connectivity.

H₃: There is relationship between social media and business performance

H₄: There is relationship between social media and authenticity & uniqueness of product

H₅: Social media affects the price of products

H₆: Social media facilitates campaign of products

H₇: Social media increases the chance of fraud business activities

H₈: Social media helps to follow trend

H₉: social media helps new entrepreneurs

Research Objectives

The purpose of the research was to determine the effect of social media on business performance in Bangladesh by investigating Arki group. The specific objectives are:

a. To quantitatively examine the effect of social media on creating brand awareness, develop connectivity, setting price of products, and marketing campaign of Arki group.

b. To quantitatively evaluate the role of social media on detecting fraud business activities, following of trend, and assistance to new entrepreneurs of Arki group.

c. To explore the relationship of social media with authenticity & uniqueness of product as well as with business performance.

Research methodology

Research Type and Approach

The type of research was exploratory as it aimed to unveil the effect of social media on business performance of a firm which belongs to real estate sector. Mixed research approach has been used although it was predominantly quantitative.

Data and sample

Questionnaires were used to collect primary data from 200 respondents which consists of managers, marketing executives, associated manufacturers and subcontractors of Arki Group. Stratified random sampling method was used to select respondents. The idea of selecting individuals from various departments was to obtain a range of viewpoints, and twenty participants from various departments offered a variety of viewpoints on the effects of social media. In designing the questionnaire, close-ended questions were used along with five-point Likert scaling technique where 1=Strongly disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree, and 5=Strongly Agree. The validity of data was checked through Cronbach alpha. As the value of alpha was 0.75 so the data were valid.

The researcher also performed semi-structured interviews with a variety of departmental heads, management personnel, heads of marketing departments of affiliated organizations, and directors to get the qualitative data. More open-ended questions were used throughout the interviews to get the interviewee to expound on his responses, which allowed for the identification of themes and patterns. In order to draw attention to the major themes and patterns that emerge from the interviews, the specifics of the conversation were documented. The target audience for the interviews came from a population that was divided into several groups. From around 90 executives, a total of 09 people were selected by purposive sampling technique for the purpose of interview. In this instance, judgmental sampling makes the most sense given the time and schedule constraints at work. According to (Saunders, 2012) “with purposive sampling researcher needs to use his judgment to select cases that will best enable him to the research questions and meet the objectives” (p.287). This approach was selected since it included a purposeful selection of participants according to their background, credentials, and area of specialization. The researcher was able to gather and compare data which helped identify recurring themes and patterns and provide explanations that were pertinent to the study's goal. Besides questionnaire surveys and interviews, the data also includes 25 different discussion threads of social media. Data on interval and ratio scales were collected. Informed consent from respondents were taken in collecting data through questionnaire and interviews. Respondents were also informed about their anonymity and purpose of the research.

Data Analysis Technique

Once the researchers completed the field surveys the data were classified and coded for entering into data processing software. The work of turning the questionnaire data into useful findings required a number of distinct activities, including the initial editing of the questionnaires, data entry, editing, and correction, data analysis, interpretation of the final results, and report preparation. Data coding is the process of converting raw data into a format that computer programs can readily perceive. This approach is vital because it uses categorization, which is a critical step in getting the raw data ready for computer processing with statistical tools.

Results and Discussions

In this section, the influence of social media on *brand awareness*, *connectivity*, *price of product*, *marketing campaign*, *fraudulent business*, *following of trend*, and *entrepreneurs* has been explored. Primary interval data were collected through Likert scaling technique where degree of agreement/disagreement were valued from 1 to 5 and midpoint 3 indicates neutrality. Several t-tests have been used to measure the influence of social media on above-mentioned factors. Relationship of social media with *business performance*, and *authenticity & uniqueness of product* has been analyzed through Chi-square tests. As shown in tables A-1 and A-2, the variables are normally distributed and free from multicollinearity problem.

Social media's influence on Brand awareness

Table 1. Influence on brand awareness

One-Sample t-Test						
Test Value = 3 (H ₀ : $\mu=3$, H ₁ : $\mu>3$)						
	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Brand awareness	.779	199	0.442	.13333	-.2166	.4833

As the value of significant level (0.442) is greater than P value (0.05), so there is no significant difference between neutral (3) and other values. This implies that H₀-1 is failed to be rejected and H₁ is rejected which means social media does not improve brand awareness.

Social media's influence on connectivity with people

Table 2: Influence on Connectivity

One-Sample t-Test						
Test Value = 3 (H ₀ : $\mu=3$, H ₂ : $\mu>3$)						
	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Increase of connectivity	8.558	199	0.0636	1.16667	.8879	1.4455

Here we can see in the table that significance value is (0.06) is greater than the p value (.05). So, there is no significant difference between neutral (3) and other values. This implies that H₀-2 is failed to be rejected and H₂ is rejected which means social media does not increase connectivity between business and customers.

Association between social connection and business performance

Chi-Square test has been performed to measure the association between social connection of people and business performance.

Table 3. Social connectivity and business performance

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.720 ^a	9	0.230
Likelihood Ratio	11.834	9	0.223
Linear-by-Linear Association	.125	1	0.723
a. 0 cells (0%) have expected count < 5.			

Here, the Pearson's Chi-Square value is 11.720 and the Pearson chi-square asymptotic significance of two tail test is 0.230 which is greater than 0.05. It means that social connectivity and business performance are not associated. Hence, H₀₋₃ is failed to be rejected and H₃ is rejected.

Association between social media and authenticity & uniqueness of product:

Chi-Square test has been performed to measure the influence of social media on authenticity and uniqueness of product.

Table 4. Social media and authenticity & uniqueness of product

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.862 ^a	12	0.867
Likelihood Ratio	7.201	12	0.844
Linear-by-Linear Association	.291	1	0.589
a. 0 cells (0%) have expected count < 5.			

Table 4 shows that Pearson's Chi-Square value is 6.862 and the Pearson chi-square asymptotic significance of two tail test is 0.867 which is greater than 0.05. It means that social media and authenticity & uniqueness of product are not significantly associated. Hence, H₀₋₄ is failed to be rejected and H₄ is rejected.

Social media's influence on price of product

Table 5 shows that the significance value (0.004) is smaller than the p value (.05). It means the social media has influence on price of product. Hence, H₀₋₅ is rejected and H₅ is failed to be rejected.

Table 5: Social media and price of product

One-Sample t-Test						
Test Value = 3 (H ₀ : $\mu=3$, H ₅ : $\mu>3$)						
	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Product price	3.117	199	0.004	.53333	.1834	.8833

Social media's influence on business marketing

Table 6. Social media facilitates marketing

One-Sample t-Test						
Test Value = 3 (H ₀ : $\mu=3$, H ₆ : $\mu>3$)						
	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Facilitates marketing	-.779	199	0.442	-.13333	-.4833	.2166

From the above table we see that the observed significant value (0.442) is more than the P value (0.05), which means that social media plays no significant role to facilitate marketing. Hence, H₀₋₆ is failed to be rejected and H₆ is rejected.

Social media's influence on fraudulent business

Table 7: Social media's influence on fraudulent business

One-Sample t-Test						
Test Value = 3 (H ₀ : $\mu=3$, H ₇ : $\mu>3$)						
	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Influence on fraudulent business	2.693	199	0.062	.4000	.096	.704

From the above table we found that the significance value (.062) is greater than p value (.05) which refers that social media does not substantially increase the chance of fraud business. Hence, H₀₋₇ is failed to be rejected and H₇ is rejected.

Social media helps to follow trend

Here we can see that the significance value (0.059) is greater than the p value (.05). It means that social media does not assist substantially to follow trend. Hence, H₀₋₈ is failed to be rejected and H₈ is rejected.

Table 8. Following trend by social media

One-Sample t-Test						
Test Value = 3 (H ₀ : $\mu=3$, H ₈ : $\mu>3$)						
	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Makes life easy	1.964	199	0.059	.30000	-.0124	.6124

Social media helps new business-comers

Table 9. Assisting new business-comers

One-Sample t-Test						
Test Value = 3 (H ₀ : $\mu=3$, H ₉ : $\mu>3$)						
	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Security problem	1.022	199	0.315	.23333	-.2337	.7004

We can see that the significance level (.315) is higher than the p value (.05) which means that the social media does not substantially assist the new business-comers. Hence, H₀₋₉ is failed to be rejected and H₉ is rejected.

The above findings of the study (sub-section 7.1 to 7.9) contradict with the findings of some authors (Taneja & Toombs, 2014; Zhu & Chen, 2015) where they showed significant impact of social media on different aspects. The reasons for the null effect of social media are digital divide, low digital literacy, and poor IT infrastructure in Bangladesh.

Insights from interviews

Many new insights were revealed after conducting interviews with firms' executives. One of the main problems marketers have had in the past is getting funding and resources for social media marketing. Budgets for social media marketing are increasing everywhere right now. These budgets are getting a significant boost, not just a little increase. Companies with digital presence typically detest sharing data. They have legitimate concerns about maintaining the privacy of personal information. However, the fact that companies that were frequently managed by one person or a small team were likely to be affected by social media. They lack precise and comprehensive data about queries, their origins, follow-ups, hits on their website, and other related information. As a result, it was impossible to quantify business performance. Nonetheless, the companies we spoke with in-depth did point to a connection between social media and online strategy and company performance.

Limitations

The study suffers from some limitations such as self-selection bias due to purposive sampling and generalization of the result from one firm. There was lack of sufficient, updated and precise information due to insufficient sample size. Primary data were not readily obtainable. Some social media users didn't want to give the exact data.

Recommendations and Conclusion

Business organizations should try to retrieve the positive effect of social media on their business performance through enhanced visibility of product and product related information, judging market demand, analyzing customers' perceptions towards product, enhanced order receipts and delivery of products to customers' end. Social media enable individuals to create and share content through virtual communities and networks, including ideas, professional interests, and other kinds of expression. Bangladesh is a developing country where the usage of digital platform is increasing day by day. The development of the nation's whole communication infrastructure is necessary for digitization. Social networking sites have the potential to be a revolutionary platform if we pay attention to the communication system. The study's result found significant association between social media and price of product. So, firms with social media platform should charge competitive price and reveal that price in digital platform with a view to enhance their turnover. Except price, social media do not have any significant effect on other aspects. So, the government of Bangladesh should take necessary measures to increase digital literacy and develop IT infrastructure in rural areas.

Future studies on the effects of social media platforms on business from other perspectives may be undertaken. It is possible to ascertain how social media affects quantitative performance metrics like return on investment and assets, inquiries, sales and reservations, website visits, and so forth. Aside from that, the benefits of small business partnerships may be investigated, such as the use of innovative sales and marketing strategies including cooperative efforts between small enterprises and organizations to provide distinctive value-based packages. Further studies can further clarify how small firms in developed and developing countries use social media and online technologies differently.

Ethical Statement

During collection of primary data, respondents' informed consent was taken. Anonymous data was not shared with any institutions or organizations. The researchers have no conflict of interest with Arki group.

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Appendix-A

Table A1: Normality tests of variables

Variables	Kolmogorov-Smirnova ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Brand awareness	.115	199	.200*	.940	199	.545
Connectivity	.126	199	.200*	.854	199	.456
Product price	.114	199	.200*	.950	199	.765
Facilitates marketing	.181	199	.200*	.839	199	.086
Fraudulent business	.174	199	.089	.794	199	.088
Makes life easy	.177	199	.081	.812	199	.090
Security problem	.244	199	.063	.762	199	.089

*This is a lower bound of the true significance. a. Lilliefors Significance Correction
 Note: Data have been compiled by the researcher, computation done on SPSS

Table A2: Tests of multicollinearity

Variables	Variance Inflation Factor
Brand awareness	5.88
Connectivity	3.76
Product price	4.28
Facilitates marketing	5.67
Fraudulent business	6.12
Makes life easy	3.52
Security problem	2.69

Note: Data have been compiled by the researcher, computation done on SPSS

Appendix-B: Questionnaire

SHAHJALAL UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY, SYLHET-3114

Academic Research Questionnaire

This questionnaire will be used only for academic purpose. The answer will be kept in confidential. Your honest judgement will be highly appreciated.

Topic: Impact of Social Media on Business Performance; A case study on Arki Group

Background information of respondents:

Name: _____ **Enterprise Name:** _____ **Contact no:** _____

Types of Business:

- Food based business
- Fashion and life style-based business
- Others (.....)

Age of owners:

- a. 19-24 b. 25-30 c. 31-35 d. 36-40 e. 41-50 f. 51 & above

Education level:

- a. Primary education b. SSC c. HSC d. Undergraduate e. Graduate

Social media usage of business enterprises:

[Please put tick (✓) mark in the boxes below the best match with you]

- 1) Do you have a social media page of your business?
a) Yes b) No
- 2) To what extent does social media influence your products trading?
a) To a large extent b) Seldomly c) Never
- 3) Which social media channels your business is most active on?
a) Facebook b) Instagram c) Snapchat d) Twitter
- 4) How often do you post on social media?
a) Very often b) Somewhat often c) Rarely

Influence of social media [please put tick (✓) mark on suitable answer]

(1=Strongly disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree)

SL	Statements	1	2	3	4	5
1	Has improved brand awareness					
2	Has increased chance to reach more potential customers					
3	Has increased chance to work with diversify products					
4	Help to maintain authenticity and uniqueness of products					
5	Has Decreased product's market price					
6	Social media marketing is more effective than other marketing strategy					
7	Has increased chance of fraudulent in business					
8	Has improved networking around the country					
9	Help to follow the trend					
10	Entrepreneurs are interested to do business on social media					

Your comment

Please write any additional information about social media's impact on business:

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